

Speciation as a product of chromosomal rearrangement in birds

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The evolution of avian chromosomes in number and structure has long been a matter of interest to evolutionary biologists. Theodosius Dobzhansky, on studying avian taxa, came across the fact that chromosomal evolution frequently accompanies speciation and thus he proposed chromosomal evolution as a potential driver of speciation and diversification. Though hundred of eukaryotic genomes have been investigated {Garg [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8]; Garg & Garg [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20]; Garg et al. [9], [21], [22]; Garg & Shrivastava [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31]} yet, comprehensive chromosomal data is available for a limited number of model organism which is somewhat heterogeneous and does not permit construction of any phylogenetic landscape of chromosomal evolution.

The sequence based characterization of chromosomal aberrations within and between species has only become feasible with next generation genome sequencing technology. This has enabled the production of draft genome assemblies, which typically have long sequence scaffolds ranging from a few to several mega base pairs. Genetic linkage maps depict the physical distance between markers on the basis of their recombination frequencies during reduction division and the mapping data for such linkage maps can be procured with FISH (fluorescent in situ hybridization) for known genetic markers. Even high optical nano technologies viz. Bio Nano, through isolation of high molecular weight DNA, can produce one to one chromosome mapping for restriction sites.

An overview of genome structure in the avian phylogeny hoisted an apparent paradox that birds have evolved an unparallel phenotypic variety with certain genome rearrangements. However, Shields (1982) did not find chromosomal differences among local populations to be associated with speciation. Rather, he observed chromosomal variability within local populations to be connected either with mechanisms that support balanced polymorphism or frequency dependent selection. Thus, it is still a riddle to resolve whether karyotypic differences between species has been instrumental in promoting the initial reproductive isolation that preceded speciation or it's an outcome of speciation.

Bickham & Baker (1979) suggested a canalization model, according to which, when an organism invades a new adaptive zone, there is a period of karyotypic change that continues until the favourable or near optimum karyotype evolves. Thereafter, change becomes primarily by genetic and morphological mechanism, not due to chromosomal rearrangements. Avian taxa seem to be consistent with this model. Those taxa that are under the phenomenon of adaptive radiation are karyotypically variable whereas those have assumed conservatism must have gone through the process of radiation in remote past. Since the age of avian lineage is difficult to determine and data available on this morphologically heterogeneous assemblage is scanty, no inference could be drawn.

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